

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

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**STUDY OF PHOSTATIC ACID AND AMMOPHOS
ACQUISITION BASED ON USED SULPHATE ACID**

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Annotation: Of extractive phosphoric acid and ammophos based on low-quality, cheap Mazidaği (Turkey) phosphorite and waste sulfuric acid in one unit, unlike the existing technology, was developed using the results of laboratory research. The description of the process carried out according to the new technological scheme was given, the parameters of the technological regime were analyzed, and the quality indicators of the received product were determined. It was found that the proposed technological scheme allows to reduce production costs and produce better quality products.

Keywords: phosphoric acid, phosphate, phosphorus, phosphorus – containing reaping minerals, sulfuric acid

**ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПОЛУЧЕНИЯ ФОСТАТОВОЙ КИСЛОТЫ
И АММОФОСА НА ОСНОВЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАННОЙ
СУЛЬФАТНОЙ КИСЛОТЫ**

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Аннотация: По результатам лабораторных исследований разработана экстракционная фосфорная кислота и аммофос на основе некачественного, дешевого мазидагийского (Турция) фосфорита и отработанной серной кислоты в одном агрегате, в отличие от существующей технологии. Дано описание процесса, осуществляемого по новой технологической схеме, проанализированы параметры технологического режима, определены показатели качества получаемого продукта. Установлено, что предложенная технологическая схема позволяет снизить себестоимость продукции и получить более качественную продукцию.

Ключевые слова: фосфорная кислота, фосфат, фосфор, фосфорсодержащие минералы, серная кислота

Introduction

Improving and modernizing the existing production of mineral fertilizers is of great importance for agriculture. Conditions of intensification of processing of natural phosphates require more complete and efficient use of phosphorus-containing mineral raw materials. The solution of that problem is through the study of physico-chemical properties of phosphate-acid systems, communication mechanisms and the speed of these processes.

Studying the mechanism and rate of decomposition of natural mineral raw materials containing phosphorus in unhardened slag made it possible to propose a number of new methods. On the basis of this method, it is planned to carry out the decomposition of phosphate raw materials in an excess amount of mineral acid [1-3].

Thus, in the performed experiments, the ratio of apatite concentrate to acid was taken as 59:41 (mass fraction), in this case, the norm of acid was 69.

Based on the obtained experimental evidence, the degree of decomposition of phosphate raw materials was determined under conditions of starting temperature of 500C, 600C and 650C. Also, the dependence of the starting time of the II stage of the process on the starting temperature of the acid was deduced. Currently, extractable phosphoric acid is obtained on the basis of phosphates and sulfuric acid

according to modern technology. Ammophos is produced by neutralization of extractable phosphoric acid with ammonia in another unit.

Buying a product based on existing technology is quite expensive. Therefore, along with maintaining the quality indicators of the product, the reduction of its purchase costs is one of the urgent issues of the day [4-6].

For the set goal, research work was carried out for the production of phosphoric acid and ammophos in a unit based on low-quality Mazidađı (Turkey) and tullan sulfuric acid, and a scheme of a new technological unit was proposed.

Mazidađı phosphorite was used as the main raw material in the research, and its composition is as follows (in %): P_2O_5 -165.5-20.3; MgO -0.6-1.1; R_2O_3 - 1.8-2.4; SO_3 -2.0-2.5; F-0.8-2.8.

Based on the results of research carried out in the laboratory, a new combined technological scheme has been developed for the simultaneous production of extractive phosphoric acid and ammophos using the obtained indicators (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Combined technological scheme [1]

The combined technological scheme, the process is carried out in the following stages:

- preparation of low-quality Mazidaği phosphorite for processing;
- of ammonia and phosphoric acid in the following ratio $\text{NH}_3 : \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 = 1.0:1.1$ ($\text{pH}=7.32$);
- fractionation of sprayed, granulated, dried ammophos.

The main devices in the combined technological scheme are the following:

- 1) F4 storage for phosphoric acid;
- 2) diluted phosphoric acid storage used in F3 phosphoric acid technology;
- 3) tanks for F1 and F2 filtrates (which are solid solutions of phosphoric acid);
- 4) drum vacuum filter;
- 5) pump;
- 6) extractor;
- 7) bunker;
- 8) do zator;
- 9) pressure tank;
- 10) warehouse;
- 11) ammoniaizer;
- 12) evaporator;
- 13) stove;
- 14) sprayer;
- 15) product transporter.

The process is carried out as follows:

Low-quality phosphorite is supplied to the hopper (8), and waste sulfuric acid is received to the pressure tank (9). The calculated amount of waste sulfuric acid is given to the extractor (7) and heated to 70-75 °C. At the same time, a dilute solution of phosphoric acid (2) is introduced into the extractor. Phosphorite is fed to the desiccator in parts for 30 minutes [7-8].

At certain time intervals, a sample is taken from the extractor and the $\text{SO}_3 : \text{CaO}$ ratio is determined. After the required time is reached, the horra is gradually introduced from the extractor to the drum filter (5) and the phosphoric acid is separated from the phosphogypsum.

The phosphoric acid taken from the filter for the first time is supplied to the tank (1), from where it is re-entered into the filter and the ammonia-forming evaporator (12). At the same time, NH_3 is supplied to this apparatus.

In order to maintain the temperature regime in the device at the required level, water vapor is supplied in directions A and B. The horra formed in the evaporator (13) device enters the sprayer (15) in the direction A, where it is cooled and separated into fractions. The produced ammofos is sent to use by the conveyor line (16).

Technological mode of neutralization of phosphoric acid with NH_3 is as follows:

Temperature, °C

20 in pickle

102 in Horra

Ammofos stay in the device (min.) 2-3

Horra content, %

H_2O 68-72

P_2O_5 total 16-18

N 3.5-4.2

pH (in hor) 4.7-5.2

The steaming process of Horra is characterized by the following parameters:

Horra's humidity, (%) at the beginning 68-72

22-25 after evaporation

Temperature, °C

80-90 in the process

Evaporation of sorghum in a separator 109-112

Moisture received from the surface $\text{kg} (\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{h})$ 22-25

Heat transfer coefficient

$\text{kKcal}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{h} \cdot ^\circ\text{C})$ 800-900

$\text{KLC}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{hours} \cdot \text{k})$ 3350-3370

NH_3 in the condensate, % 0.02

The content of ammofos received, %:

P_2O_5 months. 44-46

P_2O_5 sh 37-39

N 11.0

The influence of silicon hexafluoride acid salts on the decomposition process of apatite concentrate was studied and as a result of the study it was clarified that superphosphate is modified with both potassium and nitrogen in the presence of the mentioned salts and it was determined that it is not inferior to suitable fertilizers in terms of quality [9].

Apatite concentrate (from ApK) with the following composition (%): P₂O₅-39.4; CaO-54.0; F-3.1; simple superphosphate and aluminum plant waste (hardness 8-12% H₂SiF₆) silicon hexafluoric acid and K₂SiF₆, (NH₄)₂SiF₆ salts obtained on its basis, dust formed in the filter during combustion of phosphate, coke, silicon oxide mixtures in the furnace (in %): P₂O₅-25-28, K₂O-15.3-16.2; SiO₂-16-18; CaO-1-2; F-4-5.9; Na₂O, Fe₂O₃, as well as processed sulfuric acid with a concentration of 75% H₂SO₄ were used.

As mentioned, the K₂SiF₆ and (NH₄)₂SiF₆ salts of silicic hexafluoride acid were used to increase the production of superphosphate modified with potassium and nitrogen [10].

Conclusion

The strength of ammofos grains is 5-6 mPa. The quality indicators of the produced product show that it meets the relevant requirements. Thus, according to the proposed combined technological scheme, using cheap raw materials and waste, it is possible to buy ammophos, which is superior in quality to the products obtained in existing facilities, as a result of which costs are significantly reduced.

Studies show that with an increase in the initial temperature, the time for continuing the I stage of the process is reduced. Thus, an increase in the initial temperature has a positive effect on the rate of the process. But due to the transition to another undesirable mode of the process, it is not recommended to increase the initial temperature above the specified temperature.

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